

Microwave photonics for Integrated multifrequency Lidar / Radar System

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Abstract— Surveillance systems, both based on radio frequencies (Radio Detection and Ranging: radar) and optical signals (Light Detection and Ranging: lidar), are evolving toward multiband multifunctional systems that are putting electronic technologies under pressure. Thanks to its intrinsic high stability, ultra-wide bandwidth, low loss propagation, EMI insensitivity, and high frequency of the optical carrier, photonics can be exploited not only for optical systems but also for facing these new requirements in RF systems. In fact, microwave photonics technologies play a crucial role in the generation of very stable multi-band radiofrequency (RF) sources, and in very precise and wideband RF signal detection and digitization, guaranteeing a higher level of flexibility and reconfigurability, and the complete software-defined configuration of radar systems. At the same time they allow to implement multifrequency lidars able to synthesize tunable RFs on optical carriers, for the exploitation of RF radar techniques in lidar systems. Moreover solutions based on integrated photonic circuits allow for a reduction of power consumption and footprint thanks to the subsystems' implementation on a chip.

Keywords— microwave photonics; radar; lidar

I. INTRODUCTION

Collecting the energy which is back scattered by a target allows to obtain important information, spanning from the simple detection to the range and velocity measurements of stationary and moving objects. This is the operation principle behind radar (radio detection and ranging) [1] and lidar (light detection and ranging) [2], that both find applications fields as aerial, terrestrial and maritime security as well as parameters extraction in space based remote sensing platforms. Coherent radar systems are widely used to determine the target range, and also sense the velocity due to the Doppler effect. Nevertheless, their spatial resolution is limited by the employed signal's bandwidth, they lack in cross range resolution, and are vulnerable to radio frequency interference and jamming. On the other hand, despite suffering a stronger atmospheric attenuation and being more sensitive to weather conditions with respect to radar, lidar sensors are characterized by higher directionality and spatial resolution (suitable for solving small targets), and are commonly employed in range finders, velocimeters, and imaging systems since the '70s [3][4]. Recent works also demonstrate the possibility to apply photonic technologies in the generation and detection of microwave radar signals [5][6], implementing the photonic radar paradigm. In this scenario, combining the radar and lidar

functionalities embedded in a unique system will allow to simultaneously exploit their complimentary characteristics, providing a more complete cognition of the scene under observation. The possibility to share the same photonic core between radar and lidar also allows for a reduced increasing of the hardware complexity. A limited SWAP (size, weight, and power consumption) enable multifunctional systems to be implemented in a wide range of challenging applications, such as airborne or satellite surveillance. Moreover the use of a single laser source provides an intrinsic coherence between the two sensor, allowing the development of unprecedented target classification techniques. Here we present an innovative architecture of an integrated multi-frequency lidar/radar system based on a single mode-locked laser (MLL).

II. LIDAR SYSTEM

With reference to Fig .1, a wavelength selective switch (WSS) routes different portions of the optical spectrum of a MLL to feed both the lidar and the photonic-based radar sensors.

The proposed lidar exploits two modes of the MLL, at optical frequency ν_1 and ν_2 respectively, with separation Δf , integer multiple of the MLL repetition rate (Fig.2-B). The selected lines are then split onto two paths: a replica of modes acts as a reference signal, while the other couple is modulated by a RF local oscillator (LO) exploiting a Mach-Zehnder modulator biased in carrier suppression. Four optical tones are thus created as depicted in Fig.2-C. The two new couples of tones, separated by the frequency $2f_{LO}$, will be exploited for an interferometric estimation of the target range, while the couples separated by Δf will be used for the detection of the differential Doppler. The modulated tones are boosted by an erbium doped fiber amplifier (EDFA) and transmitted through a telescope to the target which reflects them back. The backscattered modes experience a delay time τ and a Doppler shift δ (Fig.2-D). Since $f_{LO} \ll \Delta f$ the shifts of the two couples of modes can be considered δ_1 and δ_2 , i.e. $\delta_1 = 2\varepsilon\nu_1/c$ and $\delta_2 = 2\varepsilon\nu_2/c$, where ε represents the target speed and c is the speed of light.

A circulator routes the echo signal $E_{m2}(t)$ to another EDFA and to an optical coupler where it is coupled together with the reference beam $E_1(t)$, (Fig.2-E). The re-coupled signal is sent to a photodiode (PD) where the tones are heterodyned together. Among all the generated terms, only six tones fold down to the analog to digital converter (ADC) bandwidth, as

depicted in Fig.1-F and can be digitized. Four of these tones

Fig. 1. Scheme of principle of the proposed radar-lidar system, and spectra in the different parts of the scheme.

contain the information related to the Doppler shift and one term contains the information about the target range (the direct detection between the modes separated by $2f_{LO}$).

The tones containing Doppler information can be written as

$$I_d(t) = F \exp[2\pi(f_{LO} + \delta_1)t + \varphi_1] + F \exp[2\pi(v_1 + f_{LO} + \delta_1)t + \varphi_1] + F \exp[2\pi(v_2 - f_{LO} + \delta_2)t + \varphi_2] + F \exp[2\pi(v_2 - f_{LO} + \delta_2)t + \varphi_2] \quad (1)$$

where $I(t)$ represents the output current of the photodiode.

On the other hand the term:

$$I_r(t) = G \exp[2\pi(2f_{LO})t - 2\pi(2f_{LO}\tau)] \quad (2)$$

contains the information related to the time delay. More in detail the term $2\pi(2f_{LO})\tau$ represent the phase difference experienced between the modes separated by the frequency $2f_{LO}$. Assuming $\delta_1 < \delta_2 \ll f_{LO}$, the terms $I_r(t)$ and $I_d(t)$ can be separated by means of a digital band pass filter centered at $2f_{LO}$, and a digital low pass filter (from DC to f_{LO}), respectively, as shown in Fig.1-G. Considering the range processing chain and referring to (2), the phase of $I_r(t)$ induced by the delay τ is represented by $\varphi_r = 2\pi(2f_{LO})\tau$ (Fig.1-H), and the phase difference $\Delta\varphi = \varphi_r - \varphi_{LO}$ provides the information about the range R, i.e. $R = \tau(c/2)$. Concerning the Doppler estimation, only two tones separated by $\delta_2 - \delta_1$ are required. Therefore a digital filter that spans from DC to f_{LO} is applied to the photodiode signal $[I_d(t) + I_r(t)]$ (Fig. 1-G), thus obtaining:

$$I_{dF}(t) = F \exp(2\pi(f_{LO} - \delta_1)t + \varphi_1) + F \exp(2\pi(f_{LO} - \delta_2)t + \varphi_2) \quad (3)$$

These two terms suffer to the problem of the speckle noise [8]. However, by operating a square law mixing between the two terms, the differential Doppler term can be extracted and the estimation of the frequency $\delta_2 - \delta_1$ (Fig.1-I) provides information about the target speed ε without additional noise induced by target and atmospheric turbulence [8]. Fig.2 reports an example of the results obtained during the

laboratory measurements in which a target was moved firstly toward the lidar sensor, and then pulled back. As can be seen in Fig.2-A, the detected distance first rapidly decreases from 17m to about 6m, and then increases again reaching about the distance of 20m. The velocity profile, directly calculated on the Doppler shifts, is depicted in Fig.2-B and shows that in an initial phase the target isn't moving, and after the first second is rapidly accelerating up to about 2,2m/s, according with the distance variation in Fig.2-B. When the target is stopped and pulled back, the velocity drops to zero and increases again. Finally the velocity contribution slowly decreases reaching the zero value corresponding to stopped trolley position.

Fig. 2. A) Detected distance of the target; B) Detected velocity of the target

III. RADAR SYSTEM

As shown in Fig. 3, also the proposed radar system [9] exploits a MLL, which generates an extremely precise optical pulse train with repetition rate $F_{MLL}=400\text{MHz}$ (Fig.3-A). In this case we consider a dual frequency radar. At the transmitter side, in order to generate two fully coherent modulated RF signals, a combination of two waveforms at different intermediate frequencies $IF_1=75\text{MHz}$ and $IF_2=125\text{MHz}$, the spectrum of which is depicted in Fig.3-B, is generated. The laser pulses are amplitude modulated by the IF waveforms via a MZM. Due to the amplitude modulation, the intermediate-frequency signals are transferred as lower- and upper-sidebands around each mode of the MLL (Fig.3-C). The modulated optical signal is detected with a PD, in which all the spectral components are heterodyned together. This way, a replica of the signals from the DDS is obtained at every $kF_{MLL} \pm IF_n$, with k positive integer (Fig.3-D), up to the bandwidth of the employed photodiode. The output of the PD is so splitted onto two paths, where two electrical band-pass filters (BPFs) can extract the replicas of the signals upconverted to the desired carrier frequencies (CFs), as shown in Fig.3-E. In details, the waveform generated at IF_1 is upconverted to $CF_1=9925\text{MHz}$, i.e. using the lower sideband of the 25th harmonic, and the signal at IF_2 is moved to $CF_2=2925\text{MHz}$, i.e. the upper sideband of the 7th laser harmonic. Once the two upconverted signals are extracted, they are boosted and transmitted by two parabolic antennas. The same antennas collect the echo signals which, opportunely filtered and amplified, feed the photonic receiver. Here they are coupled together and optically sampled in another MZM by the same pulse train provided by the MLL (Fig.3-F). This technique allows the sampling (a single sampling for both channels) of RF signals directly at carrier frequency, taking advantage of the extremely low time jitter of the MLL [10]. Finally 400Msample/s 12-bit ADC digitizes the photodetected

Fig. 3 Dual-band radar scheme of principle (left) and spectra (A) at the MLL output, (B) IF signals, (C) Optically sampled IF, (D) Up-converted replicas at carrier frequencies, (E) Transmitted signal, (F) ADC input signal.

signal. The two echoes are then digitally separated and downconverted to base band by means of a field programmable gated array (FPGA) embedded in the ADC, and the pulse Doppler digital processing can be implemented. Fig.3-A and -B show the range/Doppler maps of the detection about 40m/s. For this measure the S-band channel was set to generate a linear chirp with a frequency deviation of 4MHz over a pulse width (PW) of $3\mu\text{s}$, and a pulse repetition frequency (PRF) of 10kHz. For the X-channel the employed chirp had a frequency deviation of 5MHz over a PW of $4\mu\text{s}$ and again a PRF of 10kHz. These parameters give a range resolutions of about 37.5m and 30m for the S- and X- channel, respectively, as can be seen in the range profiles depicted in Fig.3-C. The coherent integration time (CIT) was set to 50ms, obtaining a Doppler frequency resolution of about 20Hz, i.e. a velocity resolution of about 1m/s in the S-band, and 0.3m/s in

In the lidar system the dual frequency technique provides velocity information immune to the speckle noise, and the possibility to adjust the frequency spacing of the employed laser modes permits to adapt the emulated microwave frequency to the observed target. The interferometric approach for the range measure guarantees an extreme accuracy despite the narrow bandwidth, allowing the use of low sample rate digital electronics. The radar system, by using a MLL as a multitone oscillator, is capable of independently manage two different radar waveforms in two different frequency bands (S and X), and the coherence among the generated signals is guaranteed, thus opening new perspectives for advanced digital signal processing techniques.

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Fig. 3. A) Range/Doppler map obtained from the S-band channel, with a zoom of the target in the inset; B) Range/Doppler map obtained from the X-band channel, with a zoom of the target in the inset; C) Range profiles of the target; D) Doppler profiles of the target.

IV. CONCLUSION

A novel integrated architecture for a multi-frequency lidar and a multi-band radar sensors has been proposed and demonstrated. Both sensors are based on a MLL source which provides the necessary optical signals to the lidar and allow the generation of RF signals for the radar.

